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DEVELOPING EFL LEARNER'S SPEAKING ABILITY, ACCURACY AND FLUENCY THROUGH INTERACTIVE METHODS

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Annotation. The article studies the implementation ways of Impromptu method into the classroom. It is fully proved the importance of Impromptu speech in teaching English language. The actuality of this article is the investigation of Impromptu method in the way of development of the speaking skills to provide communication in learning a foreign language and making EFL classroom more effective teaching environment as a facilitator.

Key words: Impromptu speech, CLT, EFL, types of speaking, interaction, monolog, dialog, polylog, role-playing, simulations.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola ogʻzaki nutq koʻnikmasini rivojlantirishda Badiha usulini auditoriyaga qoʻllash yoʻllarini oʻrganadi. Tilni oʻrgatishda Badiha usulining ahamiyati toʻliq tasdiqlangan. Ushbu maqolaning dolzarbligi xorijiy tilni oʻrganishda muloqotni taʼminlash va EFL sinfini yanada samarali oʻqitish muhitini oʻqituvchi sifatida amalga oshirish uchun nutq qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish uchun Badiha usulini amaliyotta qoʻllay bilishdir.

Kalit soʻzlar: Badiha usuli, CLT, EFL, muloqot turlari, oʻzaro aloqa, monolog, dialog, polelog, rolli oʻyinlar, simulatsiyalar

Speaking was the verbal use of the language to communicate with others [D.Nunan, “Practical English Language Teaching” 2003]. Speaking was the language skill which has been developed since childhood and preceded by listening skill at the time of speaking ability was acquired. Speaking was language skill that could be performed by any speakers of language the skills may be required natural [J. Harmer, “How to teach English” 2007]. In additional, Harmer explained that speaking in interactive an according to accomplish pragmatic goals through interactive discourse with other speakers of language and he also added that speaking fundamentally an interactive task happened under real-time processing constraints and was more fundamental linked to the individual who produces it than written. Since listening and speaking were the production skill. There was relationship each other. The ability to listen and the ability to speak because some information was gained from listening. In other words, the topic to be discussed in speaking was relevant to what that speaker has heard from another person. That’s the reason why in teaching listening was always related to speaking in speaking process between a speaker and listener. It was happened interaction between them. They use the language as the medium of the speaking in that interaction. There was a process of communication which conveys the message from the speaker to listener. A speaker had to encode the message which

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contains information. In this interaction, the students must be able to comprehend what they were talking about each other. So, the speaking could be conducted well. In solving the students' skill. It was necessary to use acceptable forms of correct language. The forms involved grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation. The students would be able to produce basic structures correctly. Besides they needed to understand words and connecting devices that link them together. Therefore, in researcher point of view, producing the spoken forms correctly is important. Such as practice provided the students with intensive experience to the language situation. In other words, the teacher could easily evaluate their accuracy and fluency. The learner would be able to produce basic structures correctly. Besides they needed to understand words and connecting devices that link them together. In producing the corrected form language, the students need the practice the language they were learning. They must practice more, more fluency they could speak. In order to speak English fluently, the students need to practice the language. This condition didn't only improve the students' speaking ability but also their pronunciation. In addition, they would be able to produce correct structure.

Brown [H. Brown, “Language Assessment: Principles and Classroom Practices”, 2004] said that Language experience on nation of correct response might enable the students to his pronunciation and improve his ability to produce short structure response. In addition, He said that to develop speaking ability in the foreign, language the students must had continual practice in communication. Such practice provided the students with intensive experience to the language situations. In other words, the teacher could easily evaluate their accuracy and fluency. Understanding of the spoken language could not simply be left to take care of itself, while a higher proportion of class time was needed to develop the ability of the students to speak. It meant that in developing students speaking ability, it was necessary to use acceptable forms of correct language. The forms involved grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation and intonation. The learners should be able to produce basic structure correctly. Besides, the students needed to understand words and the correcting devices that link together. In producing the correct forms of language, the students need practice the language they were learning. This needed reflect that practice in producing the spoken forms correctly was important [H. Brown, “Language Assessment: Principles and Classroom Practices”, 2004].

Types of Speaking

Spoken language could be monolog use and dialogue. The types of oral language are presented below:

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a. Monologue

Monologue was a spoken language that used in speech, lectures reading, news, broadcast, etc. Here, the listener would not interpret the speaker while delivering a speech whether he or she understand or not. Planned usually manifest little redundancy and therefore relatively difficult to comprehend.

b. Dialogue

Brown stated that the types of spoken language include two or more speakers. Interpersonal perorate relationship while transaction usually happened to convey factual information both kinds of dialogues would be happened among people who are familiar one to each other [H. Brown, “Language Assessment: Principles and Classroom Practices”, 2004].

Elements For Spoken Production

Harmer said that there were the elements necessary for spoken production were the following:

a. Connected Speech

Effective speakers of English needed to be able produce the individual phonemes of English but also to use fluent ‘connected’ speech which sounds were modified, omitted, added or weakened.

b. Expressive Devices

Students should be able to deploy at least some of such supra segmental features and devices in the same way if they were to be fully effectively communicate.

c. Lexis and Grammar

Students were involved in specific speaking context such as job interview, we could prime them, in the same way, with certain useful phrases they could produce at various stages of an interaction.

d. Negotiation Language

The using of negotiation language to show the structure of their thoughts, or to reformulate what they were saying in order to be clearer, especially when they could see that they were not being understood.

Still according to Harmer said that in teaching speaking, the teacher was not going to look at controlled language where students say a lot of sentences using particular piece of grammar or particular function, but the teacher look at the students’ activeness. In order words, the students were using any and all the language at their command to perform some kind of oral task [J. Harmer, “How to teach English” 2007]. There were three basic reasons why it was a good idea to give students task which provoke them to use all and any language at their command”.

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a) Rehearsal

It meant that getting students to have a free discussion, gave them a change to rehearse having discussion outside the classroom. This was not the same as practice in which more detailed study take place, instead it was a way for students to get the feel of what communicating in the foreign language really feels like.

b) Feedback

It meant that speaking task where students were trying to use all and any language they know provides feedback for both teacher and student. Teacher could see how easy they find a particular kind of speaking and what they needed to do improve. Speaking activities could give them enormous confidence and satisfaction, and with teacher guidance sensitive teacher guidance cab encourage them into further study.

Speaking Assessment

The students would learn how to be communicative in speaking English. They learn some speaking skills and develop some attitude toward speaking achievement. Therefore, the speaker must know the topic of the conversation in order to give or share of their information. In the manner of speaking course, it was important to know principle in speaking, as follow:

- a) Speaking was characterized of two or more people orally, as a speaker and listener.
- b) There were many types of oral communicative between the speaker and listener.
- c) The teacher encouraged herself to develop her speaking competence effectively.

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